

ENDOPT – ENERGY AND OPERATION OPTIMISATION

Optimise your distributed electrical systems considering CO₂ intensity,
energy costs and network utilisation

HOW CAN MY COMPANY BENEFIT FROM ENDOPT?

Overall optimisation of distributed electrical systems

Minimising electricity costs

- by using flexible energy tariffs
- by avoiding or reducing peak loads

Minimising your company's carbon footprint

IS ENDOPT RELEVANT FOR MY COMPANY?

- ✓ My business uses a lot of electricity with several locations or metering points
- ✓ My company has flexible consumption, generation, or storage facilities
- ✓ Automated intervention in the system(s) is already possible or planned

ENDOPT allows an efficient, cost-effective, and sustainable use and operation of your distributed systems.

THAT SOUNDS PERFECT! WHAT'S NEXT?

Arrange a first consultation appointment with the NEFI-team!

Step 1: Collection of the technical, economic and regulatory framework and analysis of the system(s)

Step 2: Techno-economic survey and evaluation of savings potential

Step 3: Linking ENDOPT to the system(s)

Step 4: Individualisation and customisation of the solution according to your needs and requirements

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